

Applications of Wireless Sensor Nodes in Structural Health Monitoring: A Review

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Abstract

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) strategies are used to analyze the structural response and used to effectively detect, locate, and assess damage caused by progressive environmental deterioration and continuous loading effect. Wireless sensing network (WSN) is the rapid development technology frequently used in the design and implementation of SHM system. WSN is a low cost, easy to deploy, fast and reliable technology for SHM. Wireless nodes are deployed on structure for measuring parameters like acceleration and temperature. All wireless nodes are identical to each other and have onboard sensors. These sensor nodes can receive and transmit the data from neighboring nodes which are connected in star, tree or mesh topology. The base station through multiple hop relays will receive data from the entire neighboring node. Different frequency channels and radio output power levels will gauge the performance of nodes. SHM is witnessing intense research efforts in mechanical, aerospace, maritime, as well as civil engineering applications. In this paper, a review of wireless sensor nodes and their applications in structural health monitoring is discussed.

Keywords

Wireless Sensor Networks, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), Multi-hop Communication, Review.

Introduction

There are various factors for structural health monitoring by using wireless sensor network. To estimate the structural health we need to focus on two basic factor of structural health measurement (SHM) i.e., time scale of change and severity of change. Severity shows the degree of change and time scale shows response of change with respect to time. SHM is liable to detect damages in buildings, ships, aircraft, pipelines and different effect created by natural or man-made disasters (such as earthquake, explosion, tsunamis, wind, corrosion, etc.) [1].

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For structural health monitoring, the damage inspection is generally done through two techniques: direct inspection (Visual Monitoring, X ray) and indirect inspection. Indirect inspection includes change in structural behavior. When there is no concept of WSN the wired damage detection is been used, where we deploy piezoelectric accelerometer with computers. But, the concept of WSN changes the entire scenario of SHM. Now the damage can be detected (in multi-stories building, long span bridges and dams, etc.) easily and at lesser cost. The only cost involves is towards the installation, inspection and maintenance of sensing hardware [1,2,5].

Background

Over a past few years of experiments Scientists are able to identify the material behavior used for construction through electronic devices. Structural engineers are capable of using this technology to find out the design and analyze the response of material when dynamic load is been applied on it. There are many sensors (to be used in the WSN nodes) which can be deployed on the structure to extract the useful information related to its health and transmit it to the base station [2,4]. Radar is been used in defense applications as the very first sensor network used for air traffic monitoring and detecting enemy submarine. Many sensor networks for defense applications has been developed and used earlier which includes Cooperative Engagement Capability (CEC) to hit the dynamic air target by collecting data from various sensor nodes, Fixed Distributed System (FDS), Advanced Deployable System (ADS) and Unattended Ground Sensors (UGS) are used for monitoring battle fields. These Scientific researches lead to the development of higher level communication protocols, algorithms. These days the technology has decreased the size of sensors via Micro Electro Mechanical System (MEMS) based designs. MEMS has a capability of increased range of communication, required low power for its operation and are easy in deployment [1,6]. For short Range of two-way wireless communication Zigbee is used for having low complexity and lower speed rate. Fiber Bragg gratings (FBR) are used for strain and temperature measurement. Another useful technology is been developed using optical fibers and propagation of signals is though total internal reflection. It has narrow spectrum range. When temperature changes or any load is applied on the fiber optic cable then there are changes in core refractive index which can be easily shown through signals [9]. D-ring network is been used to allow signals pass through the longest distance so that there are no data losses [2].

Working Characteristics

There are many methodologies which are used to calibrate the damage in the Structures and there are some sensors useful in the calibration process. Few of them are discussed here:

Sun SPOT

For SHM, the Sun Small Programmable Object Technology (SPOT) shown in Figure 1 can be used. Sun Microsystems Inc has developed Sun SPOT, it has an in build java embedded software development platform which provided a Java virtual machine (VM)

called Squawk. It consists of on board sensors, analog and digital I/O pins, two switches, eight tri color LEDs. Atmel AT91RM9200 is the main processor used for this system having 512 K of RAM and 4 MB of flash memory. Sun SPOT has IEEE 802.15.4 radio transceiver, antenna, main processor, memory, battery connector and power distribution circuit [1].

Figure 1: eSPOT board [1]

Strain Gauge Sensors

Measuring strain in a material when load is applied can be measured through Strain gauges [8]. For SHM, strain gauges are of an important use [6]. A strain gauge is made up of a metallic foil which conducts electricity. There are different insulated backing layers which get deformed when load is applied on it respectively the electrical resistance get changed. Proper adhesive material should be used to attach strain gauge to structures. Hence strain gauge is attached to each wireless node and transmits the data wirelessly. Calibrating defects through this process is expensive [1,2,5].

Dynamic Strain Measurement Using FBG Sensors

The Traditional RSG Sensor is been replaced by high resolution FBG Sensors which can be used for static as well as Dynamic load. Developing smart structures FBG sensor place an important role because we need large number of sensors to deploy on the structure to get useful data from it. It decreases the complexity of the system due to replacement of wire to wireless. The Sequential measurement of data from base node to node can be easily done. Fiber Bragg gratings are formed by is formed by creating periodic variation in refractive index of short segment optical fiber which reflects particular wavelength and transmits others. Periodic wavelength generates a specific dielectric mirror. Single mode fiber is been used to get FBG [2].

Figure 2: Working Principle of FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) Sensor [1]

Figure 3: FBG Strain Sensor [8]

Accelerometers:

For Structural Health Monitoring accelerometer plays an important role which is used to monitor vibrations. There are two different sources of ambient vibrations which effects our structures i.e. Earthquake and normal ambient vibrations because of thunder, wind, aircraft's, etc. ADXL202E accelerometer is used to capture big movements like earthquake while Silicon Design 1221L is used for small vibrations [2].

Figure 4: Accelerometer Board [3]

Acceleration in two orthogonal axis can be easily captured by ADXL202E and 1221L. The data from accelerometer board is converted from analog to digital then passed through low pass filter of 25 Hz and get stored in Mica2 mote and data can be send when required [2,5].

Figure 5: Block Diagram of Mica 2 Mote [1]

The 3D Accelerometer

The 3-Axis 2g/6g inertial sensor LIS3L02AQ is been embedded on Sun SPOT. It is used to locate the vibrations in all 3 axes X, Y, Z. Row of LEDs direction represent the direction of X axis, the SPOT's surface perpendicular to the row of LEDs represents Y axis and the Z axis is perpendicular to the SPOT's surface. X and Y axis can measures maximum sample rate of 4.0 KHz and 2.5 KHz for the Z axis. The signal before going to ARM9 processor following procedure takes place sampling, low-pass filtering, analog-to-digital conversion, 320Hz is maximum sampling rate at which the SPOT used [2,3].

Humidity Sensor HS220

This module converts relative humidity into the output voltage. The Humidity Sensor Board as shown in Fig 3 can be easily mounted on each node to collect information [2].

Figure 6: Humidity Sensor Board [2]

Software Characteristics

Tiny OS software is the best software used for one hop communication. The broadcast technique is used to transmit information and MintRout is used for multihop convergence routing. Reliable data can be achieved through layer above broadcast and MintRoute. To achieve signal without noise from base node, WSN faces few challenges like high sampling rate with low jitter, time synchronized sample, reliable command dissipation, reliable command collection. FTSP, MintRout and Drip is the best solution for above problems. FTSP technique is used to rectify the problem of Time synchronization and high frequency sampling can be compensated by Buffer Log. Instead of Logging component and sampling component remaining component should be off to rectify Jitters. Digital signal processing is used for reducing noise emerged from sensor nodes [1,7].

Conclusion

The design, development and implementation of Wireless sensor network in Structural health monitoring can be easily be done by using above sensors modules which is to be attached at a proper distance from the transmitting node on the structures by using proper adhesive material. TinyOS operating software is been used to achieve reliable data transmission and data collection so that quality vibrational data set can be invested. Network jitters is been limited by TinyOS. Applying WSN for SHM in Real time mode we would be able to maintain and can rich the quality of Structures and can be able to maintain the longevity of Structures [10-14].

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